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PSYCHOLOGICAL CHANGES AMONG ADULTS WITH NEUROMYELITIS OPTICA SPECTRUM DISORDER – BRIEF REVIEW

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Abstract

The aim of our article was to discuss the psychological changes of patients with Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMOSD).

Results: Patients with NMOSD have high prevalence of depression and anxiety, and abnormal stress reactions. Some of them have specific phobias, developed bipolar or major depressive disorder. The minority of patients with NMOSD exhibit behavioral and personality changes and frontal disinhibition syndrome. Most of them are reactive. However, in some cases, astrocytic dysfunction, neuroinflammation, frontal lobe lesions and specific neurotransmitter imbalance also play role.

Conclusions. Psychological changes, associated with NMOSD are very frequent, although underestimated in clinical practice. They should be taken into account and adequately treated, because they interfere with the quality of life of NMOSD patients.

Keywords: neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder, psychological changes, anxiety, depression, autoimmunity.

Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMOSD) is a relatively rare autoimmune demyelinating chronic disease of the central nervous system. The core clinical syndromes of the disease are optic neuritis, acute myelitis with longitudinally extensive transverse myelitis and area postrema syndrome (Yamout, 2026). About 70% of all patients with NMOSD are positive for aquaporin 4 antibodies (AQP4+). About 40% of all seronegative patients are positive for myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein IgG (MOGAD) and the others are double seronegative (dsNMOSD) (Yamout, 2026).

Although the developed consensus for diagnosis and treatment of NMOSD in regard to its pathogenesis, there is relatively few data for the prevalence, diagnosis and treatment of psychological changes of such patients. The aim of our article was to discuss the psychological changes of patients with NMOSD.

Depression. One of the most frequent psychological signs of the disease is depression (see table 1). The estimated prevalence of depression is 10 to near 100%, depending on the screening tool and the study population. The average prevalence of depression is about 40% of all cases (Liu, 2023). The prevalence of severe depression reaches up to 15% (Jia, 2022) with major depressive disorder in 8.9% of cases (Barzegar, 2021). MOGAD patients also have high frequency of moderate and severe depression with prevalence of 28.6% (Kogel, 2024). Despite this, patients with NMOSD are less likely to report mood signs than those with multiple sclerosis (Eaneff, 2017), although the risk for depression/anxiety doesn't differ between NMOSD and multiple sclerosis (Kwon, 2024). The additional risk factors for depression in NMOSD are poorly understood. The level of depression correlates with the level of neuropathic pain (Zhang, 2022). The risk is significantly higher among males (vs females), patients with low income, who live in un non-urban areas and among young patients (Kwon, 2024). Depression correlates with pain, anxiety and disability (Lorefice, 2025). The suicidal risk is relatively small (Correa-Díaz, 2025). The

pathogenesis of NMOSD associated depression is unclear. Depression could be suggested as reactive to a chronic disease (Esiason, 2024; Lorefice, 2025), although some authors suggest that it might be a bidirectional connection between depression and NMOSD (Cacciaguerra, 2022; Xu, 2026). Xu et al. (2026), Sun et al. (2019) and Lorefice et al. (2025) propose AQP4 antibodies might play important role for development of depression and mood changes among such patients through involvement of key frontal lobe zones and astrocytes dysfunction. Moreover, the severity of depression correlates with increased time-varying functional connectivity between the precuneus and the temporal lobe, showing specific functional changes at NMOSD brain (Cacciaguerra, 2022). Although high prevalence of depression in NMOSD, studies show low levels of medical treatment (Ayzenberg, 2021; Liu, 2023; Esiason, 2024; Lorefice, 2025). About 40-50% of all depressed NMOSD patients are not treated with antidepressants at all, although many of them tend to have moderate or even severe mood symptoms (Ayzenberg, 2021; Liu, 2023).

Anxiety. The second most frequent psychological disorder in cases with NMOSD is anxiety. The prevalence varies between 10 to 100% of cases depending on screening tool and the study sample (see table 1). Most of the patients with anxiety have moderate to severe one, cases with mild anxiety are relatively rare (Jia, 2022; Esiason, 2024; Correa-Díaz, 2025). The frequency and severity of anxiety in NMOSD correlate with pain, sleep disorders, social burden, level of disability, depression and cognitive impairment (Eaneff, 2017; Barzegar, 2021; Jia, 2022; Tong, 2022; Liu, 2023; Min, 2023; Correa-Díaz, 2025; Lorefice, 2025). However, neuroinflammation, frontal lobe changes and neurotransmitter imbalance also play role for the development of anxiety among NMOSD (Sun, 2019; Cacciaguerra, 2022; Liu, 2023; Min, 2023; Xu, 2026).

Phobia. Phobia is relatively rare among NMOSD patients, although is worse than among healthy controls

(Ebadi, 2020; Esiason, 2024; Correa-Díaz, 2025). Patients often fear of relapses and social isolation (Ebadi, 2020; Esiason, 2024).

Posttraumatic stress disorder, following diagnosis. Esiason et al. (2024) emphasized the significant stress reaction immediately after following diagnosis. Symptoms include “avoiding mention of NMOSD, somatic hypervigilance, and ongoing medical procedures acting as re-traumatization” (Esiason, 2024). It is associated with history of adverse childhood events (Esiason, 2024), although neuroinflammation and neurotransmitter dysregulation might play additional role for the severity of symptoms. However, after the initial reactions of fear, anxiety, depression, frustration, etc., most of the patients accept the diagnosis and the severity of symptoms decreases (Delgado-García, 2022). Despite this, about 30% of them remain frustrated and feel challenged for different reasons (Delgado-García, 2022).

Frontal disinhibition and behavioral changes. The minority of patients with NMOSD tend to exhibit behavioral changes such as psychological inflexibility, cognitive fusion, rigid thinking, frontal disinhibition, hallucinations and reduced full-scale intelligence quotient and dementia (Sun, 2019; Saab, 2022; Esiason, 2024; Kazzi, 2024; Xu, 2026). Sun et al. (2019) described several cases with behavioral changes due to leptomeningeal enhancement and frontal lobe lesions. Saab et al. (2022) reported a case with 1-year history of paranoid visual, auditory, and tactile hallucinations and mental retardation prior the diagnosis of NMOSD (AQP4+) with significantly improvement after corticosteroid treatment and Eculizumab.

Bipolar disorder. Bipolar disorder is relatively rare in cases with NMOSD (Correa-Díaz, 2025). In most of the cases it is coincidental (Correa-Díaz, 2025, Esiason, 2024). Despite this, Saab et al. (2022) reported a case

with bipolar disorder and NMOSD (AQP4+) with improvement of mood symptoms after starting the immunotherapy with Eculizumab. Xu et al. (2026) also presented a case with AQP4+ and bipolar disorder that improved with starting the immunotherapy (glucocorticoid, intravenous immunoglobulin and inebilizumab). Such cases suggest the role of AQP+ autoimmunity on bipolar disorder development in cases with NMOSD so in some cases mood changes should be considered and treated as specific symptoms of the disease.

Major depressive disorder. The prevalence of major depressive disorder in NMOSD is 8.9-13% (Barzegar, 2021; Mirmosayyeb, 2026). It is associated with female gender, older age, marital status, low education, migraine, thyroid dysfunction, anemia and the level of disability (Mirmosayyeb, 2026). However, in some cases it could be the initial symptom of NMOSD (Xu, 2026). The diagnosis and treatment in such cases is challenging.

Conclusions: Psychological changes and disorders are frequent among patients with NMOSD. They tend to have high prevalence of depression, anxiety and abnormal stress reactions (mostly immediately after the diagnosis confirmation). Some of them have specific phobias, developed bipolar or major depressive disorder. The minority of patients with NMOSD exhibit behavioral and personality changes. Psychological disorders might be reactive to the diagnosis. However, in some cases, astrocytic dysfunction, neuroinflammation, frontal lobe lesions and specific neurotransmitter imbalance also play role. Psychological changes are underestimated in clinical practice. They should be taken into account, diagnosed and adequately treated, because they interfere with the quality of life of NMOSD patients.

Table 1.

The levels of depression, anxiety and major depressive disorder among patients with NMOSD.

Study/article	Number of patients	Percentage of psychological changes
Barzegar, 2021	67 patients with NMOSD	Anxiety 10.4% Major depressive disorder 8.9%
Huang, 2020	210 patients with NMOSD, mostly AQP4+	Depression 10%
Beekman, 2019	44 patients with NMOSD	Depression 10.4% Emotion symptoms 7.3%
Jia, 2022	138 patients with NMOSD	Mild depression 15.9% Moderate depression 19.6% Severe depression 15.2% Moderate anxiety 42.0% Severe anxiety 58.0%
Zhang X, 2022	122 patients with NMOSD	Depression 38.5%
Meca-Lallana, 2022	71 patients with NMOSD (self-reported)	Depression 44.3%
Liu, 2023 (meta-analysis)	4213 patients with NMOSD	Depression 40% Anxiety 45%
Ayzenberg, 2021	166 patients AQP4+	Depression 39.8%
Mealy, 2019	21 patients with NMOSD	Minimal depression 42.9% Mild depression 28.6%

		Moderate depression 28.6%
Ham, 2025	635 AQP4+ patients 262 dsNMOSD	Depression 38.2%
Seok, 2022	40 patients with NMOSD (of them 34 AQP4+)	Moderate/severe depression 20%
Tong, 2022	87 patients with NMOSD	Anxiety 58.6% Depression 49.4%
Kogel, 2024	32 patients with MOGAD	Overall depression 42.9% Moderate to severe depression 28.6%
Cacciaguerra, 2022	27 patients with NMOSD	Depression 63%
Eaneff, 2017	522 patients with NMOSD (self-re- ported)	Brain fog 22% Anxiety 22% Mood swings 20%
Esiason, 2024	31 patients with NMOSD	Mild depression 26.7% Borderline depression 20% Moderate depression 6.7% Severe depression 6.7% Minimal anxiety 27.5% Mild anxiety 31% Moderate anxiety 31% Severe anxiety 10.5%
Correa-Díaz, 2025	34 patients with NMOSD, of them 23 AQP4+	Mild anxiety 17.65% Moderate/severe anxiety 58.82% Mild depression 47.06% Moderate depression 14.71% Severe depression 11.76% Adjustment disorder 5.9% Specific phobia 2.9% Bipolar disorder 2.9% Suicidal tendency 5.9%
Loreface, 2025 (systematic review)	57 articles among NMOSD patients in- cluded	Depression 40% Anxiety 45%
Mirmosayyeb, 2026	299 patients AQP4+	Major depressive disorder 13%

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